

5 Key Takeaways From webinar 1

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"The Recovery Plan and the wall of investment which is coming – the largest since the Marshall Plan – will be looking for new ways in which business and economic opportunities can respond to setting out what the economy and society of the future can be - in new businesses, value chains, innovations and platforms. The **nature-based enterprises** which feature on this platform can offer really significant **potential to deliver** on the ambitions of the **EU Green Deal** and indeed the **EU Recovery Plan**."

- John Bell, Director, Healthy Planet, European Commission

What role can Chambers of Commerce play in stimulating the nature-based economy?

"We see the potential from the nature-based economy to **up-skill our workers**, generate new sources of **employment** and **attract investment** from companies with a green corporate agenda."

- Hazel Chu, Lord Mayor of Dublin

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The **private sector** can play a key role in the **nature-based economy**. There was a high level of interest in the 'Adopt-a-Park' scheme from Nicosia (CY) where local businesses are investing in small local parks as part of their corporate social responsibility (CSR) programmes. We also heard from multiple **nature-based enterprises** who are **supplying high quality nature-based solutions** to both cities and the private sector. Engage with them through the Enterprise Platform!

Measuring impact – social, environmental and economic - is essential to financing development, fostering investment and building successful long-term NBS business models.

The Connecting Nature Enterprise Platform is a pioneering platform that supports the growth of the nature-based economy in Europe and beyond.

It connects increasing global market demand for nature-based solutions (from public and private sector 'buyers') with supply (innovative enterprises developing sustainable nature-based solutions).

Nature-based solutions come in all colours - green, blue, brown and often mixed with grey!

Community engagement is key "If we take a place based approach with a nature based solutions lens, we can look at actions that do no harm or are a positive action for **social cohesion**, health & well-being, environment, economy & biodiversity all at the same time. If an action has a negative impact on one of these areas then it is not a nature-based solution and is also not a **place-based approach**".

- Gillian Dick, Glasgow

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There was a high level of interest in the success of the **NBS cluster** in Malaga. In Brazil, for example, an NBS cluster is starting to shape up as well. What is the potential of an NBS cluster for the ignition of the nature-based economy? How can a cluster be developed? Learn more about it and exchange with speakers on our next webinar...

Register here for our next webinar

"Activating the Private Sector in the Nature-Based Recovery"

16 December 2020 at 13:00 CET

Missed the webinar? Listen to the full recording [here](#)

You can find more information and resources on nature-based enterprises [here](#)